

AMINO DERIVATIVES OF TITANIUM TETRABROMIDE. PART I

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The amino derivatives of titanic bromide have been prepared by the action of titanium tetrabromide on some mono- and di-amines, their properties studied and structures discussed.

The co-ordination number of titanium is six, but compounds in which titanium has co-ordination number of four and eight have also been reported in the literature. Ruff and Eisner (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2260) studied the action of ammonia gas on titanium tetrabromide at a low temperature and obtained titanium octaminotetrabromide, $TiBr_4 \cdot 8NH_3$. Rosenheim and Schütte (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 26, 239) saturated a solution of pyridine hydrobromide and titanic acid in alcoholic hydrobromic acid with hydrogen bromide and isolated pyridino-bromotitanic acid, $(C_5H_5N)_2 \cdot H_2TiBr_6$.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of compounds by treating titanium tetrabromide with aromatic primary amines in ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. Ether was distilled over metallic sodium. Titanium tetrabromide was prepared by the method of Olsen and Ryan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2215), redistilled at 230° and extracted with ether.

General Method of Preparation.—A dilute solution of the amine, prepared in anhydrous ether, was slowly added to the titanium tetrabromide solution with constant stirring. When just the requisite quantity of the amine solution had been added, the reddish yellow colour of the bromide solution was discharged and the supernatant liquid became colorless. The amine solution was then added in slight excess and left for about an hour. The precipitate was filtered and washed with anhydrous ether till the washings did not form any precipitate with titanium tetrabromide. It was dried at the room temperature, analysed and its properties studied. Two sets of experiments were carried out simultaneously. The results reported in Tables I and II are the average of the two values.

TABLE I

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with primary diamines.

Amine.	Compounds.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Benzidine	Dibenzidino-TB [Ti(NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ - C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂]Br ₄	Light ash- grey	> 400°	6.54	6.51	43.44	43.46	7.60	7.61
<i>o</i> -Tolidine	Di- <i>o</i> -tolidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ NH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ - C ₆ H ₃ NH ₂ .CH ₃) ₂]Br ₄	Light reddish brown	"	6.08	6.05	40.39	40.39	7.03	7.07
<i>o</i> -Phenylene- diamine	Di- <i>p</i> -phenylene-TB diamino-TB [Ti{C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂ } ₂]Br ₄	Greyish black	"	8.26	8.21	54.72	54.78	9.57	9.60
Dianisidine	Di-dianisidino- [Ti{CH ₃ O.(NH ₂)C ₆ H ₃ - C ₆ H ₃ (NH ₂)OCH ₃ } ₂]Br ₄	Purple	" 120°	5.64	5.60	37.34	37.36	6.56	6.55
<i>o</i> -Naphthylene diamine	Di- <i>o</i> -naphthylene diamino-TB [Ti{C ₁₀ H ₆ (NH ₂) ₂ } ₂]Br ₄	Deep (decomp.) crimson red	268°	7.02	7.01	46.76	46.72	8.22	8.19

TABLE II

Compounds of titanium tetrabromide with primary monoamines.

[TB denotes titanic bromide]

Amine.	Compound formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Titanium.		% Bromine.		% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Aniline	Tetranilino-TB [Ti(C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	White	250°	6.51	6.48	43.20	43.22	7.53	7.57
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Tetra- <i>o</i> -toluidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	"	221°	6.01	6.02	40.15	40.18	7.06	7.04
<i>m</i> -,,	Tetra- <i>m</i> -toluidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Light pink	243°	6.03	6.02	40.18	40.18	7.02	7.04
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	Tetra- <i>o</i> -anisidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	White	282°	5.56	5.57	37.15	37.20	6.48	6.51
<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	Tetra- <i>o</i> -phenetidino-TB [Ti(C ₂ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	188°	5.25	5.23	34.88	34.92	6.10	6.12
<i>p</i> -,,	Tetra- <i>p</i> -phenetidino-TB [Ti(C ₂ H ₅ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Light ash	285° (decom.)	5.23	5.23	34.86	34.92	6.14	6.12
Benzylamine	Tetrabenzylamino-TB [Ti(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ .NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	White	226°	6.05	6.02	40.14	40.18	7.02	7.04
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Tetra- <i>p</i> -toluidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Light yellow	302°	6.02	6.02	40.16	40.18	7.04	7.04
<i>α</i> -Naphthyl- amine	Tetra- <i>α</i> -naphthyl- amino-TB [Ti(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	297°	5.12	5.10	34.00	34.02	5.98	5.96
<i>β</i> -Naphthyl- amine	Tetra- <i>β</i> -naphthyl- amino-TB [Ti(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Pinkish white	265°	5.14	5.10	34.01	34.02	5.97	5.96
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Tetra- <i>p</i> -anisidino-TB [Ti(CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]Br ₄	Dirty white	320° (decomp.)	5.60	5.57	37.16	37.20	6.50	6.51

Bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method, nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and titanium as TiO₂.

DISCUSSION

The effective atomic number of titanium in both the series of compounds is 26, which is not a stable configuration, and therefore the compounds, though stable at the room temperature, begin to hydrolyse slowly as soon as they come in contact with water or other reagents, e.g. sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, etc. The compounds with mono-amines hydrolyse slowly at the room temperature but rapidly when heated to 50°, and Ti(OH)₄ is precipitated according to the equations:

whereas those with the diamines are more stable and hydrolyse slowly even on boiling.

On heating alone they furnish a white, greyish white or grey sublimate, soluble in water, acidic and responding to tests for Br and NH₃. The compounds with mono-amines afford this sublimate at lower temperatures than those with the diamines. When they are heated with soda-lime the corresponding amines separate out and condense in the cooler part of the tube. All the compounds respond to the diazo test.

It appears that the amines attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines, which is responsible for the greater stability of these compounds, and may be represented as :

in the case of a mono- amine, such as aniline, and the chelate compounds of the structure

in the case of a diamine such as benzidine.

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